

**THE SUBSUMPTION OF THE HUMAN SCIENCES TEACHER:
IN THE SO-CALLED “NEW” HIGH SCHOOL**

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10668732

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ABSTRACT

The present work aims to highlight important discussions on the implementation of the so-called new high school, so that one can critically analyze the panorama of the different processes involved in this context, where the performance of foundations and private institutes has constituted a true government apparatus for the elaboration of public policies aimed at the education sector, with which it was possible to articulate, materialize and consolidate political, pedagogical, ideological and labor transformations already unleashed in recent years. The suggestion of this text is that this complex scenario of power relations needs to be studied from some specific processes, such as managerialism, proletarianization and precariousness of the teaching profession, which accelerated and deepened what is identified here as the subsumption of teachers, and in the specific case of this work, a particular look at teachers in the area of Human Sciences, in which are concentrated the disciplines of Geography, History, Philosophy and Sociology directly affected by the implementation of formative itineraries that pasteurize their knowledge.

Keywords: Humanities in high school. Performance of foundations and private institutes in the reform of high schools. Precariousness of the teaching career. Proletarianization of teachers. Managerialism. Subsumption of the Humanities.

INTRODUCTION

With the implementation of the “new” secondary education, resulting from Law No. 13,415/2017, which amended the National Education Guidelines and Bases Law known as LDB 9,394/96, it was established that schools would need to progressively increase their workload for this stage of basic education by 2022. At first glance, who could find this a problem?

The movement of apparent “expansion” anchored in the defense of an integral education, a concept that is sometimes misunderstood, turns into a practical reduction in the

number of classes in some subjects, mainly in the area of Human Sciences, as the workload that previously was entirely destined to the traditional curricular components such as History, Geography, Sociology and Philosophy, now grouped by the so-called basic general training (FGB) and aligned with the teaching of skills and abilities explained by the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC, 2018), they begin to “divide space” with the so-called training itineraries.

Therefore, even with the “increase” in the total number of hours for high school, the creation of training itineraries begins to “consume” class time previously exclusive to FGB, and, consequently, the number of classes in some subjects. Behind a proposal to transform education, which according to the reform is:

To meet the general training needs, essential for exercising citizenship and entering the world of work, and responding to the diversity of young people's expectations regarding their training, the school that welcomes young people must be committed to the integral education of students and with the construction of your life project (BNCC, 2018, p.464)

The contradictions of the movements are emerging, which, in justifying a renewal of the curriculum and teaching, end up limiting the introductory and preparatory propaedeutic training for higher education courses to the detriment of the utilitarian technical knowledge represented by the training itineraries. It is worth making it clear that the previous model also had many problems, but the point is that this supposed reform, in addition to not solving previous problems, ended up creating new ones.

According to BNCC, the purpose of high school in contemporary times is that of a “school committed to the integral education of students and the construction of their life project.”

This new structure of High School, in addition to ratifying the organization by areas of knowledge – without disregarding, but also without making direct reference to all the components that made up the curriculum at that stage –, provides for the offering of varied training itineraries, whether for in-depth academic in one or more areas of knowledge, whether for technical and professional training. This structure adopts flexibility as a principle of curricular organization, which allows the construction of curricula and pedagogical proposals that more adequately meet local specificities and the multiplicity of students' interests, encouraging the exercise of youth protagonism and strengthening the development of their projects. life. (BNCC, 2018)

Integral education and the students' life project would be built through the choices of training itineraries, which could deepen studies in areas of knowledge such as Applied Human

and Social Sciences, Languages, Mathematics and Natural Sciences, or, from the perspective of a training professionalizing technique offered throughout this teaching stage.

In the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC, 2018), regarding secondary education, the need for “recreating the school” is stated, which, in turn, would need to be in line with the dynamics of technological advances and attentive to “the uncertainties regarding changes in the world of work and social relations”.

Expressions such as “flexible training”, “students’ reality”, “choice of training itineraries” and “new demands and complexities of the world of work”, permeate the entire discussion surrounding Secondary Education within BNCC, these expressions are the pillars of support of the proposal already implemented in 2022, defended in the name of the necessary and urgent modernization of the curriculum.

Given the controversy surrounding its function and execution, the implementation of training itineraries gained prominence in the mainstream media and became the subject of discussion in 2023, which ended up resulting in the suspension of its implementation for 60 days, established by Ordinance No. 399, of 8 March 2023.

What cannot be lost sight of is that these curricular reorganizations are not detached from the socioeconomic context in which they are inserted. As we know, the implementation of the so-called “new” secondary education included the active participation of congressmen, private foundations, sectors of the mainstream media and social movements aligned with the neoliberal bourgeoisie (SIMÕES, 2017).

Therefore, as expected, academics focused on this topic to reveal the different facets of this process of curricular change. More than that, they sought to point out possible consequences of this curricular (re)organization, of schools, of teaching work, of student training and fundamentally on the type of education we intend for our society.

Therefore, this work set out to carry out a bibliographical survey capable of guiding some reflections that could indicate a general panorama about the possible developments and political and pedagogical meanings regarding the “new” secondary education, and, specifically, by the cut and context of where this work is inserted, consider the impacts on the curricular components of History, Geography, Philosophy and Sociology, considering that they are now organized within the area of applied human and social sciences, and it is of fundamental importance to understand the situation, the importance and place of these curricular components within this debate.

The search movement for publications that orbited the developments of the “new” secondary education, without losing sight of the issue of Human Sciences, was in fact very

productive. Search engines such as Google Scholar, the Scielo platform, Capes journals and the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) were used.

The search for the expression “human sciences new secondary education” returned four hundred and twenty-one thousand results on Google Scholar, and one thousand nine hundred and fifty-four results on BDTD. With this information in hand, the second step consisted of filtering the points of interest that could contribute to the proposed investigation.

Within this research process, possibilities emerged to compose a line of investigation that may indicate some paths so that it is possible to understand central issues of this curricular “reorganization”. Four points were selected for analysis that could be central to the investigation of this work, and that would be capable of highlighting the current situation that involves the political and economic forces that act in the modeling of basic education curricular proposals.

The first point, which caught attention at the beginning of this research, is the large number of articles that were found on the relationships and interests of foundations, institutes and private companies in the education sector that mobilize and influence the debate on curricular reforms to from their ideological perspectives aligned with neoliberalism.

When (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022) discuss the performance of Brazilian business, from the perspective of the Gramscian concept of private apparatus of hegemony (APH), in which social organizations financed and organized by private capital end up acting decisively in the BNCC's curricular construction and of the “new” secondary education, as if they were seeking to meet the general desires of the nation, it is evident that the interests of the dominant class sought to direct public educational policies to meet their specific interests, mainly aiming at the “productive restructuring process” , or can we believe in the kindness of the business community in spending its resources without interest in return?

Evidently, these interests are directly linked to the process of (re)allocation of capital immobilized by the structural crisis and intrinsic to the capitalist mode of production, enhanced by the decline in the participation of Brazilian industrial activity in GDP in recent decades, therefore, capital moves to new sectors and areas where public authorities aligned with neoliberal perspectives act in their favor, as

“the social metabolism of capital in the process of bourgeois recomposition, promoted a takeover of the State by the bourgeoisie, where as a coercive apparatus with the function of spreading its ideals and adapting human beings to the new social needs of production...” (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022, p.11).

The second point concerns what researchers have called managerialism, a process idealized by a set of publications directly linked to and disseminated by private capital

foundations, and which began to be followed and executed by education departments and different school managers, both private and public networks, aiming at a policy of controlling teaching work.

Seeking to enable the internalization and practical organization of this ideology within the school, with the purpose of resembling them or transforming them into companies, managerialism becomes the perfect ideological apparatus for the valorization of private capital in which teachers come to be seen as “workers”, where the actions to be performed are planned by third parties and teachers go from being producers of knowledge to reproducing information pre-prepared by educational systems.

costs and benefits, innovation, skills, reactivity, adaptation, entrepreneurship, good practices, flexibility, pragmatism, immediacy; always do more, always better, with less; goals, projects, in short, a subtle framework of control mechanisms that guarantee the fabrication and construction of the consent and consensus of a subjected subject. (SOUZA, 2020, p. 21)

Which brings us to the third point, which deals with the precariousness and proletarianization of the teaching profession. The pressures and interests of an expanding “market” on the privatization of education, targeting the State itself as its main client, whether in the supply of teaching materials or pedagogical advisory services or even according to some bills still being processed in some states and city halls, in which the private sector seeks to act on the so-called “shared management”, where it assumes the role of managing basic education schools, increasingly bringing the reality of schools closer to the management logic of their companies.

This process consists (PAVAN & BACKES, 2016) of limiting or preventing teachers from having access to decision-making spaces that involve everything from the pedagogical proposal to the very act of planning classes. External assessments and booklet systems are the expression of this process, because as what needs to be studied is already defined by these devices, criticality regarding the objects of knowledge and discussions about didactic procedures and referrals are seen “as a waste of time”.

The last and fourth point, but not least important, is to understand how all three of these factors mentioned pressured the reorganization of the curricular components that condense History, Geography, Philosophy and Sociology within the area called Applied Human and Social Sciences. Does this reorganization aim to provide an interdisciplinary reflection on the phenomena studied, or is it a pasteurization of superficial knowledge that relegates the epistemological tradition of these sciences?

Therefore, this research can contribute to the organization, systematization and chaining of discussions that are scattered across academic digital research mechanisms, and here, the effort is created to place them in a joint perspective, contributing to drawing a panorama overview of the processes that involve the curricular transformations of the New High School in Brazil, in compliance with its objective and material constraints resulting from the metamorphosis of neoliberal capitalism that moves towards sectors where the exploitation of further work has not yet reached its peak, and could yield a First, large profits and, secondly, the production of a citizen aligned with their own political and ideological interests for the configuration of contemporary society.

NEOLIBERAL AND BUSINESS INTERESTS IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR

First of all, it is necessary to ask ourselves why large businesspeople, linked to the retail, banking and media sectors, began to have their interests focused on the educational sector at the turn of the last century?

The cyclical crises of the capitalist mode of production and the process of deindustrialization of the Brazilian economy, accompanied by a financialization of the activities of these same entrepreneurs, mobilized their capital to areas where the extraction of the most value had not yet been fully developed. Education, scrapped by the public authorities for years, is one of these areas. The state apparatus is taken over by the bourgeoisie, which begins to spread its ideals through the monopolization of the debate that directly impacts the management of public resources applied in different sectors of the country (SOUZA, 2015).

The justification for such a movement is covered by a supposed interest of well-doing businessmen who claim to want to contribute to the development of education and science in the country, when in fact they seek to consolidate and consolidate their economic influence over the education sector that opens up to the large capital (KOSSAK & VIERIA, 2022), this process is a direct consequence of the efforts of a neoliberal State that meets the desires of the bourgeoisie that appropriates the function of the State itself, and that is effective in transferring political “powers” to this class Social.

For the expression “entrepreneurs” to gain shape and name, it is necessary to highlight the most illustrious people interested in profiting from education, to know who are the political actors who influenced the main changes in education in recent years and who actively participated in the discussions that guided the formulation of the BNCC and the so-called “new” secondary education, for example.

The first group to gain prominence in the mainstream media was the movement called Todos Pela Educação (TPE), which receives funding from large companies and organizations, such as Itaú, Natura, B3 Social, Fundação Lemann, Fundação Bradesco, Gol, ifood, Fundação Roberto Marine among others. Constantly called upon to give their opinion on the interests, directions and financing of basic education, as well as on its curricular reforms in the mass media, a space never granted to student and teacher movements, who to society appear as wards and incapable of knowing what which could be better for education, even though those are directly interested and affected in this process.

Another prominent actor within this political game is the Lemann Foundation (FL), despite being part of the TPE, it has a very strong independent and more objective role in the educational market, which will be the subject of analysis in the following paragraphs. And completing this scenario, at least in the possible scope of this work, the Ayrton Senna Institute (IAS) stands out, which in recent years has developed reports and diagnoses to guide the execution of public educational policies, including the “training” of public managers.

In this way, we have a cut within the general panorama of those who were most present at the National Congress, influencing and influencing the discussions, and consequently, reducing the spaces for other sectors of society such as teachers' unions and student movements. These last two, even though they tried to build resistance, proved to be insufficient as political organizations. (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022).

In fact, in the light of history, today it is possible to say that the reform of secondary education was widely expected by these businessmen mentioned, just remember that right after the “coup farce of May 2016” (SOUZA, 2017, np) one of the first agenda to be approved in congress along with the labor reform was the reform of the “new” secondary education, carried out through a provisional measure, which only reinforces the thesis that the change was not widely discussed nor approved by those who genuinely they should be the biggest stakeholders, students and teachers.

What we need to understand is the existence of a political dispute over the meaning of this “new”, as well as the set of expressions that fill and structure the construction of the text of the BNCC itself and the projects headed by these private initiatives that seek to bring to themselves the responsibility to promote and influence the progress of the implementation of this new curricular framework.

This is another point of attention that we need to pay attention to, the text. Both from the BNCC and other documents influenced and produced by these organizations. When talking about flexible training, for example, the National Common Curricular Base goes “in the

direction of replacing the single high school curriculum model with a diversified and flexible model” (BNCC, 2018, p 468). Such a process would need to be guaranteed by offering “different curricular arrangements, depending on the relevance to the local context and the possibilities of the education systems” (BNCC, 2018, 468).

It is possible to notice that these definitions used by the BNCC are very broad and not very precise, subject to different interpretations that may favor certain groups and their economic and ideological objectives, which were identified here as those most interested in these transformations, than in fact a project to elevate the development of education in the country within a critical and democratic perspective.

The expression “flexible” starts to be used both in the BNCC and in other texts that support its theoretical assumptions, a consequence and direct reference to the Toyotist model, where the “Just In Time” production reorganized the circulation flows of capital and the hand of labor itself. constructions. With this, the analogy is made and makes it clear that for certain groups, interested in reformulating education due to the need to prepare individuals adapted to this new productive logic, “the business community needs to spread its ideals, reaching the formation of human beings, shaping them for the flexible market” (KOSSAK & VIERIA, 2022, p.12).

Regarding the part where it talks about “local context and the possibilities of education systems”, it leaves the question so open that from this premise and due to precarious structures, such as the lack of teachers and low investments, schools it started to offer only one training itinerary, at most two, and without dialoging with this life project, as it does not allow students to deepen their studies in the areas they want, as their choices are limited.

This is true political and media fraud, as what was defended as justification for implementing this reform was precisely the fact that students could “build” their training path aligned with the interests and demands of contemporary society, which in practice It didn't happen, mainly in public education, but also in the private network in smaller schools. Which, in turn, tends to increase inequality between the poorest and the richest, given that private schools with greater infrastructure are able to offer greater diversity in these itineraries. (CASSIO & GOULART, 2022)

Therefore, the movement intended here with this discussion is to relate this ideological framework of expressions that fill the discussions around high school curricular reform with the process of curricular appropriation of these organizations, foundations and companies regarding education. In addition to these expressions and their political and ideological meanings, and so that the discussion we intend to establish can develop into other spheres, let

us take as an example what the TPE, the Lemann Foundation and the IAS have developed in recent years by consolidating their presence in the education through its political-economic actions.

ALL FOR EDUCATION – (TPE)

The TPE is constituted as a civil society organization, but when we analyze its organizational framework and supporters we will see that the Brazilian business elite is completely involved in this project, from the councils to the coordination and presidency, they are largely occupied by businesspeople. The TPE presents a line of action more focused on the intellectual training of professionals directly involved in discussions about the direction of education in the country, which can be divided into three axes,

“Articulation and Institutional Relations – aims to encourage debate and mobilization; Communication and Mobilization – aims to increase the inclusion of the Basic Education theme in the Media; and Generation of Technical Knowledge – monitors and analyzes official educational indicators.” (MARTINS, 2013, p.85).

According to TPE itself:

“We work to qualify the public debate and promote the mobilization of key actors in Brazil who can positively impact the advancement of priority public policies for Basic Education. We are an active voice in the press and social media in order to make the topic of Education the number one topic in Brazil.” (ALL FOR EDUCATION, 2022, p.10)

This action by the TPE takes place in such a structured and organic way that its group of intellectuals, in addition to its work within the third sector, also becomes part of the first sector, occupying positions within the National Education Council (CNE) as well as in the case of Mr. Francisco Aparecido Cordão (adviser and former president of the TPE), and the former minister of education Fernando Haddad (founder), and also the former minister and former president of the National Education Development Fund, José Henrique Paim Fernandes (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022).

Another very important space for the TPE's activities is the mainstream media, because as we have seen, the Roberto Marinho Foundation itself is one of its supporters, which certainly facilitated its public presentation as an important and sometimes central actor in the debate on the necessary educational reforms. that the country would need.

Their representatives invariably appear on the Marinho family's broadcaster's newscasts

to clarify, resolve doubts and guide the debate on issues ranging from budgets to curricular reforms, a projection that has not been achieved by any other group, much less those linked to teachers and their unions. “The TPE imposes upon itself the task of leading changes in educational policies in Brazil and, at the same time, putting into practice a nation project.” (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022, p.14)

It is in the axis of activity, identified as Generation of Technical Knowledge, that the TPE has achieved great success, as, by producing a set of publications and materials that support its vision of the reality of Brazilian education, constructed by people who work directly and indirectly in In the area of education, the TPE gains the legitimacy and credibility to influence the debate around the formulation and public policies.

Through its report “With an eye on goals”, which aims to measure data relating to the development of Brazilian education, of course, fully aligned with the assumptions of teaching skills and abilities defended by UNESCO, OECD and PISA, “the TPE, by At the same time that it establishes itself as a reference for the media and researchers, it equips society to monitor and demand from governments for education along the lines proposed by the TPE” (MARTINS, 2013, p.89).

Within this panorama, the TPE also presents the following publications, such as the “MEC Budget Monitoring Panel”, “PNE Observatory”, “State Panoramas”, “Municipalities Panel” and the “FUNDEB Simulator”. These publications clearly seek to guide discussions about the direction of education from a certain vision, which fundamentally always comes to influence its articulation with the State.

Its “Institutional Relations” front has been building points among “businesspeople, media professionals, representatives of international organizations, third sector leaders (...) government representatives and public education managers” (MARTINS, 2013, p.108).

As a result, the TPE has increasingly become the business community's interlocutor with the State, maintaining close and somewhat promiscuous relations to the extent that its group of founders and members begins to be confused with the state apparatus itself, because as it was here As evidenced here, it is common for positions in the Ministry of Education and its departments to be occupied by people directly involved with the TPE.

Therefore, it is possible to see that the business community uses the TPE to directly influence public educational policies in accordance with their interests, relying on the work of the mainstream media to legitimize their actions and disseminate their perspectives directly or indirectly and on a group of researchers and technicians who use expressions that orbit pedagogical discussions and the corporate world to rethink and reorganize the curriculum,

whose ultimate objective is that these proposals are capable of influencing the debate, but “in order to detach the TPE from its business origin, at the same time in that his project seeks to respond to the historical demands of Brazilian society” (MARTINS, 2013, p.145).

LEMANN FOUNDATION – (FL)

FL emerged in 2002 and since then has been gaining ground and guiding debates surrounding education in Brazil. According to information on the FL website, which defines itself as “a family philanthropy organization, created in 2002, out of the desire to build a fairer and more advanced Brazil.” To make this possible, FL claims to act on two strategic pillars, Education and Leadership, “two fronts capable of boosting our people and generating real changes” (FUNDAÇÃO LEMANN, electronic document, s/d)

In its “desire to build a fairer and more advanced Brazil”, the FL is getting closer and closer to the State, and it is exactly in these two axes, Education and Leadership, that the FL is consolidating its initial actions and displacing the role of the State itself. for the private sector. (OLIVEIRA, 2021)

What initially appears to be a philanthropic organization is gradually metamorphosing into a public and private partnership (PPP), and the State is becoming FL's main “client” as its programs, publications and services seek to guide the very actions of this State are seen as inefficient.

In the first years, he worked on creating training programs for teachers, coordinators and managers, as in the case of the Management for Learning (GPA) course, offered and adhered to by different state governments, which was extensively analyzed by PERONI & OLIVEIRA, 2020 in State of Alagoas, and as well as the Innovation and Connected Education Program (IEC), started in 2017 in partnership with the MEC, the Ministry of Science, Technology, Innovation and Communications, BNDES and the Fundação Itaú Cultural, whose objective would be to support the universalization of access to high-speed internet in basic education.

But it was from 2011 onwards that investments increased and actually entered the market. Since then, FL has expanded and started to operate through and through other organizations, now targeting the educational platforms and systems market, in addition to financing a large number of publications related to planning, classroom methodologies and textbooks.

FL publications focused on teaching practices already permeate discussions within

schools, as large education networks have started to adopt some of these publications as references for coordinating pedagogical work, as is the case of the SESI-SP network, where the book entitled “Planning for understanding” by authors Grant Wiggins and Jay McTighe, it is widely used both in teacher training and in pedagogical meetings, serving as a model to be followed for the production of planning for teaching activities.

But it is from 2021 onwards that a new way of operating for FL opens, now with the effective acquisition of schools. According to a report by Estadão, published on February 26, 2021, through the educational group Eleva, billionaire Jorge Paulo Lemann snapped up 51 schools that previously belonged to the Kroton group, which is now under the umbrella of the Cogna Educação holding company. It is worth mentioning that Eleva has an educational platform that is one of the products of the Somos Educação group, which in turn is also part of Cogna Educação.

The owner of AMBEV, Americanas, Burger King, among others, now has 120,000 students across Brazil under his responsibility. Within FL it is necessary to highlight its other associated organizations, such as Nova Escola, Reúna, MegaEdu, Movimento pela Base, Instituto Gesto and Bem Comum.

These organizations with their respective publications began to permeate the daily lives of coordinators, teachers and students, offering lesson plans, reports, courses and various educational materials all aligned with the BNCC and the new secondary education, in addition to providing solutions for numerous secretariats of education spread throughout Brazil. It is estimated that this market can generate R\$70 billion annually in Brazil, not bad for a foundation that claims to be philanthropic.

Therefore, we can already observe that in fact the FL has nothing to do with a philanthropic family organization or any other legal definition such as institute, association, etc., all these definitions are social masks to try to hide what in fact the FL is a group of businesspeople with clear interests in the educational market are that they seek, through their activities in the third sector, to disseminate a political-economic ideology “as a way of materializing human formation that will favor the consolidation of financial capital” (OLIVEIRA, 2021, p.103).

Thus, behind this supposed philanthropic commitment to improving education in Brazil, FL now has the State as one of its main clients, whether through PPPs, consultancy services or even published books, these are “Third Way strategies to in order to make use of public resources, in the form of services” (OLIVEIRA, 2021, p.104).

FL has been expanding its partnerships and forms of action, carrying out true mediation

work between public and private entities. Partnerships with the Ministry of Education (MEC) and the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research (INEP) have become increasingly common.

Furthermore, FL has managed to partner with the MEC to bring teaching platforms to Brazil, such as Khan Academy, which, since 2011, has contributed to the development of Mathematics teaching, as well as other platforms of which it is a partner, namely: Coursera, responsible for distance learning courses, Programaê, Geekie, Youtube Edu and many others, especially after the pandemic (2020), because the Systems are being influenced to maintain remote teaching, requiring the appropriation of platforms by students, mostly from Google. (OLIVEIRA, 2021, p. 108)

And to guarantee the legitimacy of these proposals, guiding political discussions within federal chambers, FL began to act directly in the training of leaders through its Lemann Fellowship program, which has a partnership with the largest universities in the world. After all, who would question someone who graduated from Harvard, Stanford, Oxford and Columbia? Institutions where their leaders are trained receiving scholarships financed by FL.

And it is precisely from these places that their trained leaders began to import texts and authors to permeate the pedagogical work within schools, as in the case already mentioned here of the book *Planning for Understanding (Understanding by design)* by authors Grant Wiggins & Jay McTighe, book published in Brazil by Penso Editora in partnership with FL and Instituto Canoa, currently used by the SESI-SP network to guide the planning of teachers' pedagogical work.

In this process of disseminating the school management model to be followed, the Nova Escola association has played an important role. Also claiming to be non-profit and supported by FL, it is a digital platform with lesson plans, educational materials, training, courses and reports whose objective is “to strengthen Brazilian teachers and is accessed by around 3.1 million people per month” (NOVA ESCOLA, electronic document, s/d).

In this way, the platform acts as a facilitator with more than six thousand free lesson plans aligned with the BNCC, facilitating and shaping teaching work to the curricular assumptions built with great participation from FL.

AYRTON SENNA INSTITUTE – (IAS)

Like the other organizations mentioned so far, the Ayrton Senna Institute (IAS) is a non-profit foundation with no party political ties, and its purpose is to develop studies and diagnoses to guide and execute public policies in the area of education. An example of this action is its

leading role during the implementation of the BNCC and the reform of Secondary Education. He was one of the most active voices within this process, as well as one of the most heard by traditional media.

Today the IAS has the massive support of large business groups, such as Itaú, McDonald's, Volkswagen Group Foundation, Microsoft, Visa, Boeing, etc. After all, which large companies today do not support a cause as fair and unquestionable as education, and also represented by an institute named after a great Brazilian sportsman known worldwide?

As we can see, the IAS's operating strategy is very similar to FL and TPE, and in many situations partnerships between the three are formed. The IAS is yet another organization that is justified by the State's slow and inefficient actions in driving the changes necessary to improve education in the 21st century, and as a result, some partnerships began to be established between the IAS and state and federal governments, such as This is the case of the “Educational Solution for Secondary Education” in 2012 with SEEduc/RJ, in the State of Rio de Janeiro, widely analyzed by KOSSAK & VIEIRA in the work “Atuação do Entrepreneurship in the New Secondary Education”, as well as in the process of implementation of the comprehensive education and socio-emotional skills project in support of the education department of the government of the State of São Paulo.

Comprehensive education and the development of socio-emotional skills are two of the main objectives of the IAS, even used as success stories in the institute's 2021 annual report, in which this integral education would be justified on the need to prepare students for the future , but without necessarily explaining exactly what that future would be, and where socio-emotional skills would be the big gap to be developed by teachers.

Specifically on socio-emotional issues, there is a mapping carried out with more than forty thousand educators, whose objective would be to favor the integral development of students with a view to the well-being and professional satisfaction of teachers. According to the 2021 IAS report, “the initiative encourages frequent dialogue between teachers and students, building a formative process of development and self-knowledge for both”.

In this way, the IAS acts directly in the “training” of groups of trainers in the state education departments, who are responsible for transmitting and disseminating these concepts to the managers and teams of the schools involved. It also involves the reconfiguration and reorganization of a flexible curriculum, differentiated from the existing one, while developing a flexible matrix of cognitive and socio-emotional skills. (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022).

It can be concluded that for the IAS, the changes towards quality education are not directly linked to the necessary valorization of the increasingly precarious teaching career, nor

does it address the issue of increasing social inequalities between layers of the population, nor the precarious school structures and equipment, but rather due to the need to develop socio-emotional competence and the lack of motivation, both among students and teachers.

Behind this movement is the construction of a concept of Integral Education within the rationality of the institution itself. These strategic and progressive actions allow the IAS to build consensus around its educational project. And which ultimately culminate in the institutionalization and legitimization of the implementation of “public education policies, through legal normative devices, where the IAS ideology becomes a transformation in the concrete and everyday reality of Public Education” (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022, p.18).

Perhaps one of the greatest contributions of the IAS, especially since it became a UNESCO chair and received the support of the OECD as its partner, is the dissemination of teaching based on skills and abilities based on cognitive and socio-emotional dimensions. And it is precisely in this partnership that was mentioned here with SEEduc/RJ that the teaching of competence and skills, whether cognitive or socio-emotional, worked as a kind of pilot project so that they could later guide the BNCC itself and the High School Reform. (KOSSAK & VIEIRA)

Therefore, in the light of these latest analyzes on the FL, TPE and the IAS, the interests of capital, represented by these organizations, present themselves as modern and technically supported solutions to change Brazilian education, and for this their publications and partnerships act consciously to build a consensus on their conceptions.

Thus, capital's action strategy, which manifests itself both in supranational organizations and in the social reasons of the institutes and groups presented above, has as its main objective the construction of consensus regarding capital's educational project. In this way, we observe that both the TPE and the IAS have the same common steps and strategic steps carried out to achieve society's consensus regarding their educational project of capturing the subjectivity and shaping the psychophysical nexus of Brazilian youth, the working class in training (KOSSAK & VIEIRA, 2022, p.20)

In this way, we can resort to the concept of private apparatus of hegemony (APH) developed by Antônio Gramsci, where the author leads us to understand that the private sector seeks to use its structures and organizations, as in the case of these foundations and institutes mentioned, apparently distinct and without political and economic ties to their own companies, which take upon themselves the functions and discussions that would initially be public and conducted by the State, appearing as a kind of apparatus of the State itself.

The hegemonic apparatus is understood, therefore, as a particular society

(formally private), which becomes the correspondent of the governmental-coercive apparatus. Strength and consensus, the two inseparable halves of domination, the two halves of the Machiavellian Centaur, both develop their respective “apparatus”. (HOEVELER, 2019, p.149)

Therefore, the concept of APH helps us understand that in fact the foundations analyzed here, whether FL, TPE or IAS, all of them result from the mobilization of financial resources from their supporters and partners to enable the articulation and functioning of a project for Brazilian education, counting on broad influence in the sphere of political debates, whether in congress or in the mainstream media, in order to influence the direction of educational policies to consolidate a new type of student, a new type of citizen, which is now formed According to the ideological assumptions of these same maintainers of the functions, “we see here that the installation of a hegemonic apparatus is equivalent to a “philosophical reform”: to the extent that it creates a new ideological terrain, it effects a reform in consciousness and in the methods of knowledge” (HOEVELER, 2019, p.150)

This “philosophical reform” is directly linked to the fact that the labor relations that make up the productive arrangement of the national bourgeoisie need to be reorganized to meet the new needs of the composition of this capital, in order to guarantee the competitiveness of its companies in the international market. .

The promotion of entrepreneurship and support for sustainable development and employability and the development of strategies for the formation of social capital are used as ideologies capable of guaranteeing social harmony and forming a consensus around the validity of the market logic argument as an element sufficient for the regulation of society. (SOUZA, 2022, p.4)

It is no coincidence that in different education networks, whether public or private, the entrepreneurship itinerary has ensured its presence in the first steps of the implementation of the Secondary Education reform. Different researchers have dedicated themselves to understanding how this training can impact the precariousness of work in the lives of these students (MENEZES, 2023; IVO, 2022; PRADO, 2020).

This process of reformulating secondary education has been decisive in disseminating and persuading students to naturalize new work relationships through precarious modalities that transfer all responsibility to the working class, including expenses that a priori should be covered by the bourgeoisie, having in view of current labor legislation. Expressions such as “protagonism”, “social entrepreneur”, “sustainability”, etc., consolidate a worldview where labor rights are seen as unnecessary and even a problem for increasing the supply of jobs. When in practice we know that the labor reform, which was implemented following the High School

reform, made labor legislation more flexible at several points and the expected increase in the number of job offers did not happen.

MANAGEMENTALISM

Complementing this process of capital's advance on education in Brazil, it is necessary, in addition to the monopoly of political discussions, to be present in the management of daily school life. We will see here, that the foundations and organizations mentioned in the previous item and throughout this work, will act to disseminate and institutionalize what several researchers (OLIVEIRA, KRAWCZYK, SOUZA, KOSSAK & VIEIRA) identify today as *managerialism*, contributing to restrict or eliminate the spaces for collective construction of eventual political-pedagogical projects and proposals, directly affecting the constitutional principles of democratic management, replacing them with manuals and guidelines to be followed by teachers, coordinators and managers, all perfectly designed and without the need for further questioning about the paths chosen by BNCC, for the reform of secondary education and teaching systems controlled by large educational conglomerates that begin to monopolize the discussions that permeate teaching work throughout the country.

It is no longer news that neoliberalism, aware of the weaknesses of the capitalist system, constantly seeks to reform the State in its favor. Throughout the 20th century, we witnessed a “reinvention of liberalism through neoliberalism” (SOUZA, 2020, pg.21), in which the State was constantly influenced and reorganized to facilitate the penetration of capital in sectors where services were previously public, such as health, security and education.

However, in addition to its theoretical-economic framework, neoliberal business needed to consolidate itself as an ideal, sedimenting and expressing its ideology beyond its investments, but in the formation of a new type of worker/citizen. Expressions that once represented the intentionality of entrepreneurs and echoed within factories already influenced by Toyotism and the transformations of the third industrial revolution, such as versatility, flexibility, skills, strategic planning, entrepreneurship, know-how, etc., gained echo within the discussions that began to guide the process of school organization and planning.

The school is not only part of the capitalist system, it reproduces the dominant ideology and establishes the condition and limit for its reproduction. As Pierre Bourdieu explains to us

It is probably due to an effect of cultural inertia that we continue to consider the school system as a factor of social mobility, according to the ideology of the “liberating school”, when, on the contrary, everything tends to show that

it is one of the most effective factors of social conservation, as it provides the appearance of legitimacy to social inequalities, and sanctions cultural heritage and the social gift treated as a natural gift. (BOURDIEU, 1998)

The logic of productivity, goals and result indicators gained increasing strength and space from the 90s onwards, and became essential within this logic following the consolidation of PISA as an instrument at the service of the OECD to measure the educational development of countries. .

The internal and external visibility of adopted procedures and achieved results is another characteristic of the “New Public Management”. Through the publicization of procedures and results, this new managerialism suggests effective control of the process and product, not only by public servants (permanent or contracted), but also by the population in general, under the pretext of promoting participation and social control by users (or customers) of the public service. (SOUZA, 2017)

Today, external assessments have become the final objective to be achieved, which in turn has contaminated the very training process of students who would need to be prepared to do well in external tests, certifying that certain essential learning would be guaranteed.

To be prepared for the world of work and adapt to new market demands, different political actors and financial groups began to influence the direction of education, initially interested in two central objectives. One of them, as we have already pointed out here, is to expand the process of capital accumulation to sectors that are historically still “little” explored, such as education. The other, the expansion of the sphere of ideological influence over the political-pedagogical project of future generations, thus aligning the two objectives and modeling the standard citizen and their social life (SOUZA, 2020).

The growth in the influence of these organizations and corporations, of entrepreneurs and businessmen materializes through Todos Pela Educação, a global movement with its representations on a national scale, directly interfering in the “public” policies of Nation-States, mainly in the scope of education, as demonstrated by the construction of the PDE and PNE in the Brazilian case. (SOUZA, 2020)

As previously mentioned here, the TPE is the embodiment of the “pedagogy of capital” (SOUZA, 2020, pg.23), its financing by a large number of companies is not the result of a crisis of social conscience due to the obtaining of astronomical profits through the exploitation of the working class, but its political-pedagogical materialization that seeks to transpose its values to the public sphere, since this, in turn, has not been able to train students who meet the interests and criteria of international assessments, as it does not provide quality teaching.

The private sector presents itself as a management model to be followed, showing itself

as the one that will change educational policies for the better, as it knows what is necessary to train and prepare students for the job market, as in this new project they will emerge competitive, flexible and entrepreneurial young people, adapted to competition and will be able to overcome adversity (SOUZA, 2020), lucky for us to have the benevolence of these benefactors.

A concrete example of this process is the training program for public school managers developed by FL and Elo Educacional in 2016 (OLIVEIRA, 2021, pg.181) in which a supposed “better use of time in classroom management” should be developed by teachers, because it is logical, if education does not present the results expected by external evaluations, it must be the fault of the teacher who does not know how to manage his class time or plan his actions, and this would have nothing to do with the precarious conditions of work and the intensification of the proletarianization process of the teaching profession, the subject of discussion in the next item.

PRECARIZATION AND PROLETARIZATION OF THE TEACHING PROFESSION

It can be said that the points analyzed so far were structural in order to achieve the teacher's proletarianization process. In addition to the ideological influences disseminated and implemented by private capital, hidden by its foundations and institutes, resulting in curricular reforms, educational policies, the teaching of skills and abilities, whether socio-emotional or entrepreneurial, or even as the very logic of managerialism as a model of school management, in fact, what makes all this logic and its implementation viable given the fragility of the organization of teachers as a class, is what several researchers believe (Pavan & Backes, 2016; Alves, 2009; Rodriguez, 2008; Rêses, 2012 ; Santos, 1998) have identified the proletarianization of the teaching profession.

Fundamentally, when we talk about proletarianization, we imagine workers leaving the factories after their exhausting shifts of long working hours, who, alienated from the production process and unaware of the importance of the social division of labor, are not aware of the expropriation of the most value carried out by the bourgeoisie. .

They are also subjected to market instability that constantly puts their wages and jobs at risk, and, consequently, their very survival. What matters to the owner of capital is not in fact what is being produced, nor its use value, the product of work must have the capacity to generate profit. This is precisely the logic that has been implemented in schools throughout the 20th and 21st centuries, that of productivity (ALVES, 2009).

As the transformations in the world of work advanced, driven by technical and technological developments, resulting from the process of reorganization of capital, which in turn reorder production relations within factories, assumptions unfold from this logic that could also be applied in other spheres, including school.

Expressions that previously served to identify industry transformation processes, such as 3.0 or 4.0, were naturalized within pedagogical publications about the transformation of education itself and didactic-pedagogical relationships. The very logic of “Just in Time” developed by Toyotism penetrates the BNCC vocabularies and other documents, such as flexibility, competencies, skills, personalization. (ALVES, 2009)

The act of “clocking in” and the sound of the signals indicating the times for activities and “productions” to take place carry with them a symbolic meaning that makes the school a mirror of the factory, as it brings teachers and students closer to the reality of the factory space. Thus, like workers with their training and repetitions, teachers began to follow instructions on how to “teach classes”, or how to become productive and efficient within the so-called class hours, fractions of fifty minutes in which certain objectives had to be met. determined by didactic systems that are foreign to the reality in which they are used, but which have become the drivers and evaluators of the educational process and the teaching work itself.

The so-called class hour, to which the vast majority of teachers are subjected, derives from the logic of remuneration for factory work by the hour or by pieces. Perhaps this is the most perverse and little discussed mechanism, even by class organizations, and which deepens the process of formal subsumption (MARX, 2015) in the face of capital.

It is worth highlighting that this logic produces different effects and results, for obvious reasons, between private and public teachers. It is also worth noting that the way Marx uses the concept of formal subsumption is designed for salaried work in the context of industry, however what is intended here is to transpose the principles of this category to understand the reality of teachers' subsumption in relation to their separation of the means of work and consequently, looking especially at teachers in the private network, in which they are fundamentally valuing the capital advanced from investors, that is

The question of the subsumption of labor to capital is the question of how and in what ways, in the determinations of yesterday and today, capital subordinates and subjugates the means of production (composed of means of labor and objects of labor) and the labor force – in the sense of being able to lead them, in their combination, to the production of value under the logic of capital. The control elements that enable the subordination and subjugation of work processes for the production of

value and for the valorization of this produced value are, therefore, the privileged matter of the subsumption of work to capital. (SERAFIM, 2018, p.512)

Class time is the most evident instrument of expropriation of teaching work. Because in this logic, the teacher's work is only counted and paid for what happens within those fifty minutes. All the time spent during preparation, study and organization, which is much longer than the fifty minutes in the classroom, where intentions materialize and are expressed, is not remunerated.

The formal subsumption process would already be carried out within these fifty minutes, where part of this time would already be enough to produce the value necessary for his remuneration, but the capitalist is not satisfied with just this more absolute value, he needs to intensify the extraction of this more value in its relative form (MARX, 2015), which within a factory would be guaranteed by the implementation of technologies that would expand production capacity, but in schools this production capacity is increased as the teacher takes on a large part of the work to your home, assuming all the costs of the means of work.

This post-class work time, where theoretically the teacher should reflect on his own practice, identifying the impacts caused by his teaching action on the students' development process, producing records that support his pedagogical action to ensure that everyone involved in the process were having their development monitored, is not remunerated. Therefore, it runs the risk of not being carried out, and when it is, it falls within this process of expropriation of more work.

In this way, the proletarianization process is guaranteed. Teachers are unable to plan their classes the way they could and would like, as they do not have this paid time. To guarantee their monthly remuneration that allows them to survive, they end up working in two or three schools at the same time and accumulating a very high workload in the classroom, given the low value of the hours/classes.

Therefore, the part of the time in which the teacher is paid is in the classroom and all the work that needs to be done before and after, in addition to not being paid, is not carried out. A structural barrier is in place that will prevent teachers from planning their individual pedagogical actions.

If the teacher doesn't have time to prepare and then check, who does? Of course, the didactic systems. It is precisely in this structure that the figure of teaching material emerges to fill a space that should be the teacher's act of planning. In this way, we have the condition and limit of the proletarianization process where the teacher is prevented from reflecting on his own

teaching practice (PAVAN & BACKES, 2016).

This logic of work forces teachers to give up planning, analysis and even evaluation, as the teaching systems themselves send the assessments that must be carried out, which are already based on external models such as PISA, SARESP, ENEM, etc.

As a result, the teacher no longer understands his work and becomes another cog in the mechanism of alienated production, failing to even understand the meaning of his action as a teacher, as he has been reduced to the role of reproducer of commands, deepening his subsumption into the “ external control, progressively decreasing their capacity for autonomy and resistance” (PAVAN & BACKES, 2016).

HUMAN SCIENCES IN HIGH SCHOOL REFORM

The overview presented so far sought to contextualize and highlight fundamental points for understanding the processes and movements involved in the curricular reorganization of the so-called new secondary education, so that it would now be possible to specify discussions about the role and place occupied by Human Sciences within this process. .

Nothing more appropriate than a specialization work in Human Sciences to investigate the extent to which these curricular, political, labor and ideological reorganizations impact on the components of History, Geography, Philosophy and Sociology, considering that they are now organized within the area of knowledge called Applied Human and Social Sciences.

To do so, it is necessary to consider right away that the Human Sciences are not a thing or knowledge in itself, but as the name itself says, an area of concentration, which, in fact, comprises a variety of epistemological, conceptual, theoretical specificities and methodological and constitute “a broader movement in the history of modern science” (SIMÕES, 2017, p.48).

With the new secondary education and its training itineraries of Applied Human and Social Sciences, aligned with the conception of a neoliberal education, as evidenced here in the previous items, the difficult task of resistance and permanence of History disciplines is once again established. , Geography, Sociology and Philosophy within the basic education curriculum.

It is not new that these components have not ensured their existence within the school. The reduction in the number of Geography and History classes within the so-called basic general education, and the possibility of Sociology and Philosophy disciplines becoming hybrid, a euphemism for part of their studies and activities to be carried out remotely, or in some cases even even suppressed, goes against the recent achievements of making these

subjects mandatory, which were once again consolidated from 2013 onwards in the National Curriculum Guidelines for Basic Education, and perhaps we are once again witnessing the pasteurization of this knowledge that can impact the human and scientific training of various generations.

The permanence of these disciplines, and the possible form in which they can be acquired, are directly linked to the power relations established in the context of the class struggle, taking into account the interests and material and objective demands of the current phase of development of capitalism. In this way, it can be inferred that the presence of these subjects within the school curriculum is once again not assured, perhaps it never was, but somehow the Human Sciences began to occupy an important space within the students' pedagogical development process (SIMÕES, 2017), and despite constant attacks on its permanence, it has been resisting.

It is also necessary to consider that at the time of researching and writing this work, the current Brazilian government, elected in 2002 with the Lula/Alckmin ticket, has just announced on April 4, 2023, through the MEC and the Minister of Education Camilo Santana, the suspension of the implementation schedule of the so-called New Secondary Education.

The dissatisfaction of teachers, coordinators and students, amplified by the actions of student movements, the teaching class and other political and social groups involved with the education agenda, which are beyond the interests of foundations and private institutes that are directly and economically involved. Interested in maintaining the reform, they pressured the current government to establish dialogue with these sectors and perhaps redefine the direction of the "reform".

However, thinking specifically about the Human Sciences, it is necessary to consider and without losing sight of the fact that each of the components of this area of concentration carries with it:

i) the game of power relations that are installed in the intellectual political field of each curricular component and its scientific trajectory, the production of its theoretical-conceptual contributions, teacher training and the movements that led to their inclusion in school curricula; ii) the political field of public educational policies, their actors and interests; iii) the class struggle more broadly in the space-time of development of historical capitalism, which allows us to demonstrate that this place was never stable, fixed and safe (SIMÕES, 2017)

Therefore, it is not just a corporatist discourse that aims to maintain its existence within a slice of the teaching market, ensuring teachers of the Human Sciences components their professional existence, but the importance that each of these components have in training is

highlighted here. of students, given the very context of the implemented reform, which ironically can be perceived, discussed and criticized precisely through the eyes of professionals trained in the so-called Human Sciences.

The importance that this area of knowledge represents in giving meaning and understanding to facts that a priori, in appearance, would be isolated and decontextualized in relation to the subjects involved is highlighted here. The importance of History, Geography, Sociology and Philosophy lies precisely in providing a theoretical and methodological framework that allows students to build inferences about the reality in which they live, contributing to the fact that class relations and their respective inequalities have constituted the society in which they live. This perspective, even within the BNCC and the New Secondary Education, is still maintained and valued, even if under a guise aligned with the characteristic expressions of the reform.

Human Sciences must, therefore, encourage ethical training, a fundamental element for the training of new generations, helping students to build a sense of responsibility to value: human rights; respect for the environment and the community itself; the strengthening of social values, such as solidarity, participation and protagonism aimed at the common good; and, above all, concern about social inequalities. It is also up to the Human Sciences to cultivate the formation of intellectually autonomous students, with the ability to articulate categories of historical and geographic thought in the face of their own time, perceiving human experiences and reflecting on them, based on the diversity of points of view. (BNCC, 2017, p.355)

Now, at the same time as putting the teaching of Human Sciences in these terms, it is possible to see that the expressions “make less rigid, more dynamic, flexible, open to changes” (SIMÕES, 2017, p.52) leave open what if desired. What at first may seem like a mere question of syntax, hides the process of subordination of the Human Sciences that start to serve a training process aligned with the neoliberal interests of training for the job market.

As a practical example of this process of subalternization, we can analyze the training itinerary of the Human Sciences area, called “*Culture in movement: different ways of narrating the human experience; Technology in the narratives of social relations*”, offered by the state education network of São Paulo, which has five (5) components, the first being on cinema, and can be developed by teachers of Art, Portuguese Language, English Language or History . The second component, called “*Digital culture and physical activity*”, taught by Physical Education teachers. The third component, “*We, robots: sociocultural and work relations in the digital world*”, taught by History, Sociology or Geography teachers. In the fourth component, “*Social and technological relations: literature in evolution*”, taught by Portuguese and English

or History teachers. Finally, in the fifth component, called “*Technology, communication and culture*”, which can be taught by Philosophy, Sociology or History teachers.

Therefore, the process of subalternization of the human sciences is evident, insofar as an itinerary in this area has wide participation of language teachers, and the reason for the choices between the different teachers of History, Geography, Sociology and Philosophy when they are those indicated in certain components. There is no reference to the specificity of these teachers within the five components, which leads to the conclusion that it does not matter which Human Sciences professional will teach, what is happening is a pasteurization of the sciences.

Although the presentation of the support material states that the itinerary's main objective is to offer “contextualized learning that favors the deepening of the skills and abilities of Basic General Training and the development of the skills of the structuring axes (MAPA, 2022, p.7), Further on, in the description of the components, the skills and abilities to be deepened are mentioned, and the most ironic thing, if it weren't tragic, is that the skills are in the area of language.

basic general training skills and abilities to be deepened are EM13LGG701 and EM13LGG704. This is repeated again in component 2 with the skills EM13LGG501, EM13LGG701 and EM13LGG704. Only in components 3 and 5 do History skills from basic general training appear. They are EM13CHS101, EM13CHS102, EM13CHS403 and EM13CHS404. In component four, language skills are again highlighted. How can an itinerary that calls itself Human Sciences prioritize the area of Languages most of the time?

In this scenario, the role of HC will be subordinated and subordinated to the interests of capital, as Geography, Philosophy, Sociology and History will be worked on based on the reform, with a predominance of the business-neoliberal character. It seems that those who believe that critical thinking, capable of expanding our ability to understand how society works, is synonymous with “indoctrination” – as is the case of the Escola Sem Partido movement –, have taken an important step in the institutionalization of their ideals. However, we cannot lose sight of the possibilities of collective resistance, not only so that CH continue to occupy a place of power in school curricula, but so that public schools can be a common space in our territories for a dignified life for everyone, emancipatory, opinion-forming and subject-forming in contemporary times. (SIMÕES, 2022, p.56)

Therefore, what is at stake here is that the reduction in the number of History, Geography, Philosophy and Sociology classes within the so-called Basic General Training will make it impossible for students to have contact with knowledge and content that the training itineraries do not include. Furthermore, they will be unable to complete their process of theoretical and methodological development regarding the traditions of these disciplines, whose

importance is widely reflected in different devices and curricula as already mentioned here.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

What was sought with this research was the possibility of constructing a panorama, among other possibilities, that would enable the interpretation of the process of subsumption of Human Sciences teachers within the reform of the so-called new secondary education.

The authors mentioned, the concepts rescued, reinterpreted and used, sought to theoretically substantiate what every teacher who lives day to day in schools already knows, but which needs to be systematized so that the class itself can organize itself to press for changes.

It is hoped that it has become evident that the Brazilian business elite, hidden by the actions of their foundations and institutes, have become increasingly present, often constituting themselves as a private apparatus within the state structure itself, influencing and determining the direction of public policies for the education sector.

Within this process, others develop concomitantly, such as the issue of managerialism and consequently the precariousness of the teaching profession, which articulate and materialize the exclusion of construction and decision-making spaces that could be occupied by students and teachers, but which are relegated to the condition of subjects alienated from the process of pedagogical construction of the act of teaching and learning, where didactic systems become the condition and limit of learning experiences, given the control established by the logic of the hour/class.

Perhaps this was the most important contribution of this research, identifying the structural function performed by the logic of hours/classes. Although everyone knows about its existence, it is still little discussed and explored at a theoretical and scientific level, at least in the research carried out it was not possible to find anything at this level of specificity of discussion.

Who knows, this work could constitute a future master's project, where this issue can be deepened, seeking to look at the logical existence of the hour/class as a device of power, already making reference to Michael Foucault's concept of device, which is intended to be mentioned in the arguments of this work. As well as deepening the possibilities of conceptual transposition of the process of formal and real subsumption discussed in Marx's Capital.

Regarding the concept of hegemonic private apparatus, it is possible to find an extensive bibliography that reflects the actions of private capital from the perspective of the Gramscian

concept, but which was used here to substantiate what is observed about the actions of supposedly philanthropic foundations and institutions.

Therefore, it is believed that this work was capable of mobilizing and proposing new lines of investigation to understand the process of subsumption of teachers, from different axes, and that in the specific case of this work, how all this directly impacts the continuity and existence of the Human Sciences components in the curricular matrices, which are now pasteurized by the implementation of the so-called new secondary education, and which, due to ideological interests aligned with neoliberalism, seeks to train students based on basic skills and abilities that allow them to adapt and form the hand of work intended for capital reorganizations.

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